

Portugal

3rd wave survey - 2023

Age group

Data collection was carried out in **8 schools** and involved **771 students**.

Gender distribution

SES distribution

On average, adolescents reported **knowing very well** how to do 73% of the activities on digital **communication and interaction**, but only 40% of the activities related to **information and navigation**.

Self-reported performance on skills increases with age for all groups of digital skills. Boys had on average 46% of information and navigation skills compared to girls who had 34% of these skills at a high level.

Knowledge items*

The average of correct answers to digital knowledge is 57%. The percentage of correct answers related to digital knowledge is similar between boys and girls and increases with age.

* Respondents answered a set of questions designed to measure their actual knowledge about how the internet and digital technologies work.

How digital literacy levels increase in adolescents who participated in three waves (598)?

In 2023, the **communication and interaction** dimension had the highest level of high digital literacy (on 66% of the skills and knowledge elements) and also had a larger increase (9%) over the three years. The lowest level (44%) was related to **information and navigation**.

Communication and interaction

Content creation and production

Information and navigation

Digital literacy* is a combination of digital skills and knowledge regarding how the internet and digital technologies work.

*The levels of digital literacy are a merger of self-reported high-level skills and the correct answer on the knowledge items. For technological and operational skills digital literacy could not be accounted for due to a lack of knowledge items.

Digital literacy increases with age. Boys present higher digital literacy levels (56%) in comparison to girls (53%). Although they have higher self-report digital skills at a high level, girls have higher levels of knowledge items (58% to 56%).